

NFDI4Earth

Deliverable D1.1.1

Annual Report on Progress of Pilots 2022

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2023-05

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.7895675](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7895675)

nfdi4earth.de

Citation

Veronika Grupp. 2023. *Annual Report on Progress of Pilots 2022 (NFDI4Earth Deliverable D1.1.1)*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7895675>

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Acknowledgement

This work has been funded by the German Research Foundation (DFG) through the project NFDI4Earth (DFG project no. 460036893, <https://www.nfdi4earth.de/>) within the German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI, <https://www.nfdi.de/>).

Executive summary

The first cohort of Earth System Science Pilots started successfully in 2022 and presented their progress at project mid-term in October 2022. The pilot coordination office (PCO) represented by Veronika Grupp held regular individual progress meetings as well as thematic group meetings both online and at the NFDI4Earth Plenary in Dresden. The PCO established regular exchange and collaborations within and beyond the consortium. The draft for the second call for pilots in spring 2023 was approved by the steering group.

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1 Activities and Progress

1.1 Highlights

- Kick-Off Meeting of 1st Pilot Cohort (April 5th, 2022)
- NFDI4Earth Plenary Meeting (June 9th and 10th, 2022)
- Mid-Term Progress Reports (October 19th and 21st, 2022)

1.2 Project Start

Most of the pilot projects (11) started between April-June 2022, another 2 projects started in August 2022 and the 14th will probably start in 2023. PIs of all 14 projects participated in the online Kick-Off event on April 5th, 2022. The Kick-Off consisted of project presentations by each pilot, followed by discussion and the expression of interest for overarching topics to form thematic clusters.

1.3 Project Progress

The majority of pilot projects are in line with their proposed working plan. Due to the period of 2 years between project selection in 2020 and start of projects, three projects had a major restructuring of the project plan. 2 projects reduced their work packages, because goals set in the proposal turned out not to be feasible within the project scope. With each running project the PCO held individual progress meetings every 2 months (see Appendix). On October 19th and 21st 2022 the 13 projects presented their mid-term progress reports in a public online meeting with around 40 participants on each date mainly from within the NFDI4Earth.

1.4 Involvement of pilots in NFDI4Earth:

At the first NFDI4Earth Plenary meeting in Dresden (June 9th and 10th, 2022) the PCO presented the pilot measure and lead 2 break-out sessions. Representatives of 11 pilot projects were present to engage in discussion with fellow pilots and the NFDI4Earth community.

As initiated in the kick-off meeting thematic clusters of pilot projects emerged. A group of interested researchers participated in 2 meetings on data cubes (general exchange and technical introduction), another group of pilots interested in metadata standardization met once. A group of four pilots from the geochemistry, geophysics and palaeontology domains have regular meetings every month with occasional participation of the PCO.

1.5 Preparation of 2nd Call for Pilots 2023

The PCO has developed a draft for the 2nd Call for Pilots in February and March 2023. This included discussions among Co-Applicants and other NFDI4Earth participants, research on review procedures and exchange with other NFDI consortia. The procedure and text for the call have been approved by the steering group on Dec 16th, 2022.

2 Outputs

2.1 Milestones and Deliverables

Due to the postponed start of the first pilot cohort, the milestones and deliverables related to the end of the first project phase (MS1.1.2, D.1.1.5) were also postponed to March/April 2023. The present annual report is the first and only deliverable as described in NFDI4Earth proposal for 2022.

2.2 Overview of results

Current overview of the results by end of 2022, more pilot results are expected by the end of pilot phase in March 2023 and will be included in the next annual report.

Results by pilots:

- Maximilian Söchting (Universität Leipzig): Lexcube, an interactive visualisation tool for data cubes: <https://www.lexcube.org/>
- GeoFRESH pilot: <https://github.com/flowbio/hydrographr>
- World Settlement Footprint STAC catalog: <https://geoservice.dlr.de/eoc/ogc/stac/collections>

Results by the pilot coordination:

- Plenary Meeting NFDI4Earth, Gläserne Manufaktur Dresden, June 9th and 10th, 2022, presentation on pilot measure, <https://nfdi4earth.de/kick-off-review>
- The NFDI4Earth Pilot website was re-designed and short summaries of each project of the first cohort were added: <https://www.nfdi4earth.de/2participate/pilots>

3 Evaluation and lessons learned

Delayed project starts and change of project plans: The delayed start of some of the pilot projects was mainly caused by difficulties in finding skilled candidates. To maximize the use of available funds and to cater to the challenging recruitment situation, in the next pilot call start of projects will be even more flexible to allow an early start for pilots with suitable candidates at hand and to give more time for hiring to other projects. Furthermore, the first cohort of pilots was selected during the application phase of NFDI4Earth. Due to the evaluation process of the whole consortium, the actual project start was ~1.5 years after the project selection. For some pilot projects parts of the developments were already done with other funding or collaboration partners changed throughout those 1.5 years. To avoid major change of plans in projects in the next cohort, we will keep the time between funding decision and project start short.

Thematic pilot clusters: Apart from the geochemistry/geophysics/paleontology cluster, the other thematic groups of pilots did not evolve into regular meeting series. Participants seemed interested but also busy with the work on their specific project and other duties. Furthermore, the overlaps and possibilities for collaborations are in many cases not obvious and may be more of experimental nature or based on informal exchange. In the future the PCO will work towards a higher identification with the goals and the core product maintainers and developers of NFDI4Earth and willingness for (interdisciplinary) collaboration of pilot participants. This will be achieved by offering more spaces for discussion and exchange with other NFDI4Earth product developers and participants and providing more information on the goals and ideas of NFDI4Earth.

Budget and Human Resources: In the PCO the planned personal employment was implemented without any major deviations from planned budget. Apart from one project all pilots started in 2022. However, thanks to the approved transfer of funds to 2023, the provided flexfunds for the first cohort of pilots can be fully exploited.

4 Collaborations of the PCO

4.1 Within NFDI4Earth

- Regular attendance of the PCO at Co-Applicants meetings to stay updated on the various developments within the consortium, foresee possible collaborations of pilots with other members of the consortium and get feedback on own developments (e.g., the 2nd call for pilots, a restructured review procedure for the call).
- Involvement of the PCO in the expert group *Users* that was established to investigate user needs for the OneStop4All (creation of user stories and user scenarios, preparation of

surveys). The PCO supported the expert group by bringing in opinions and experiences by researchers of the pilots that are potential users of the OneStop4All.

- The PCO supported TA3 and TA2 in the preparation of interviews and surveys with pilot projects provide a crucial input for the gap analysis in TA3 and to assess potential user needs in the User Support Network and the OneStop4All.
- Representation of NFDI4Earth at the Open Science Festival Hannover (August 30th and 31st, 2022) together with colleagues from TA1 and TA2, to create greater visibility of the pilot projects and other measures of NFDI4Earth and connect with the broader community.

4.2 Across consortia

- In preparation for the 2023 second call for pilots, the PCO reached out to 9 other NFDI consortia¹ to exchange best practices and ideas for the review process of flexfund calls within NFDI consortia.
- Exchange and collaboration with NFDI4Biodiversity was initiated in a first online meeting (November 9th, 2022) of representatives of both consortia.
- It was followed by a more specific exchange among the PCO and the use case managers of NFDI4Biodiversity (use cases are counterparts to pilots/incubators) to foster collaborations among the projects e.g., in the 2023 pilot call.

5 Outlook

In the first months in 2023 the PCO's focus will be on the 2nd call for pilots alongside project closure of the first cohort (January – May). This includes further preparations for the call, like setting up the submission tool, the review panel and templates for both applicants and reviewers. The PCO will be contact person throughout the call and oversee the review process. Based on the feedback by NFDI4Earth architecture components we will define the format and structure of the roadmap and other deliverables by pilots of the first round. Furthermore, the PCO continues to assist TA2 and TA3 in their survey among 1st cohort pilots for the gap analysis. The first cohort will finish between March-September, pilots of the second round are expected to start between July-November. We will deepen the collaborations with NFDI4Biodiversity and keep up the regular exchange with other Task Areas within the consortium.

December 22nd, 2022, Veronika Grupp for the Pilot Coordination Office

¹ KonsortSWD, NFDI4Culture, NFDI4Ing, Text+, NFDI4Health, NFDI4Microbiota, NFDI4Biodiversity, NFDI4Chem, DAPHNE

6 Appendix

6.1 Meeting attendance of group meetings

Group/Occasion	Date and number of participants
Kick-Off Meeting 1 st Cohort	05.04.22, 35 participants
Data cube/Model Data Integration Cluster Meeting	02.05.22, 6 participants 18.05.22, 8
Geochemical/geophysical Cluster Meeting	Every first Friday of the month (January 2022)
Metadata Cluster Meeting	04.05.22, 8 participants
NFDI4Earth Plenary Meeting	09. & 10.06.22, 13 participants of pilot
Mid-term progress report	19. & 21.10.22, 40 participants

6.2 Meeting attendance of individual meetings for projects of 1st cohort

Descriptions of each pilot project: <https://www.nfdi4earth.de/2participate/pilots>

This list does not include email exchange or short phone calls, but only in-person or online meetings with more detailed exchange on the project progress in 2022.

Pilot Project	Dates of individual progress meetings
Bathy4All: Workflows for Multibeam Processing and Visualization	03.05.22, 11.10.22
Enhancing Earth System Model Evaluation with DataCube enabled Machine Learning	02.05.22, 25.08.22, 05.10.22
Developing tools and FAIR principles for MetBase database	21.04.22, 05.08.22, 24.11.22
German Marine Seismic Data Access	21.04.22, 21.06.22, 15.08.22, 15.11.22

Pilot Project	Dates of individual progress meetings
GeoFRESH: Getting freshwater spatio-temporal data on track	27.04.22, 07.10.22
Linking Environmental Data into European Scale Research Infrastructures (start in Jan 2023)	02.05.22, 02.08.22
NFDI for seamless Earth System Model-Data Integration	20.04.22, 19.07.22, 06.09.22
OcMOD: Observations closer to Model Data	04.05.22, 18.07.22, 13.09.22, 12.12.22
PAMbase: a Repository of Soundscape Recordings to study Earth's Phonosphere	14.04.22, 27.07.22, 13.10.22, 13.12.22
Reusability of Data with complex semantic structure	14.04.22, 14.09.22, 02.12.22
World Settlement Footprint	29.04.22, 28.07.22, 19.12.22
Interoperability and Reusability of geoscientific lab data	13.05.22, 28.07.22, 11.11.22
Statistical learning to assess the factors underlying environmental changes	16.08.22
Data Cube Visualization	07.04.22, 21.07.22